

TECHNOLOGICAL QUALITY TRAITS OF DURUM WHEAT (TRITICUM DURUM) CULTIVARS AND ADVANCED LINES

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Abstract. In this study, conducted at the irrigated experimental fields of the Jizzakh region of the “Scientific Research Institute of Rainfed Agriculture,” the technological quality traits of 26 newly developed durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) lines were comparatively evaluated against the check cultivar “Makuz-3” Grain samples were analyzed for thousand kernel weight (TKW), hectoliter weight (HLW), vitreousness (KV), grain protein content (GPC), gluten content (GC), and the gluten deformation index (GDI). The results revealed that 13 lines exceeded the standard in terms of TKW and HLW, while 12 lines demonstrated superior vitreousness. Furthermore, nine lines exhibited significantly higher protein and gluten content compared to “Makuz-3.” Correlation analysis indicated a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.91$) between TKW and its biochemical composition (protein and gluten), confirming the potential to simultaneously achieve both larger and higher-quality grains. Based on these findings, lines such as Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Ouasloukos 1, Bicredera1//Ossl1/Stj5/3/Ammar and Krupinka were identified as promising primary sources for durum wheat breeding programs.

Annotatsiya. Tadqiqotlar Jizzax viloyatida joylashgan Lalmi dehqonchilik ilmiy-tadqiqot institutining sug‘oriladigan dala tajriba maydonida o‘tkazildi. Bunda 26 ta qattiq bug‘doy (*Triticum durum*) tizmalarining texnologik sifat ko‘rsatkichlari andoza “Makuz-3” naviga nisbatan qiyosiy baholandi. Don namunalari 1000 don vazni, natura og‘irligi, don shishasimonligi, don tarkibidagi oqsil va kleykovina miqdori hamda kleykovina deformatsiyasi indeksi (IDK) bo‘yicha tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, 13 ta tizma 1000 don vazni va natura og‘irligi bo‘yicha, 12 ta tizma esa shishasimonlik darajasi bo‘yicha andozadan ustunlik qildi. Bundan tashqari, 9 ta tizmada oqsil va kleykovina miqdori “Makuz-3” naviga nisbatan sezilarli darajada yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi. Korrelyatsion tahlil qilinganda 1000 don vazni va uning biokimyoviy tarkibi (oqsil va kleykovina) o‘rtasida kuchli musbat bog‘liqlikni ($r = 0,91$) ko‘rsatdi. Olingan natijalarga asoslanib, Ter 1//Mrf,

Tdicocum 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Ouasloukos 1, Bicredera1//Oss11/Stj5/3/Ammar va Krupinka kabi tizmalar qattiq bug‘doy seleksiyasi dasturlari uchun istiqbolli boshlang‘ich manbalar sifatida tanlab olindi.

Аннотация. Исследования проводились на орошаемом опытном поле Научно-исследовательского института богарного земледелия, расположенном в Джизакской области. В ходе исследования была проведена сравнительная оценка технологических показателей качества 26 линий твердой пшеницы (*Triticum durum*) по отношению к стандартному сорту «Макуз-3». Образцы зерна анализировались по таким параметрам, как масса 1000 зерен, натурная масса, стекловидность зерна, содержание белка и клейковины, а также индекс деформации клейковины (ИДК). Результаты показали, что 13 линий превзошли стандарт по массе 1000 зерен и натурной массе, а 12 линий продемонстрировали преимущество по степени стекловидности. Кроме того, было установлено, что у 9 линий содержание белка и клейковины значительно выше по сравнению с сортом «Макуз-3». Корреляционный анализ показал сильную положительную связь ($r = 0,91$) между массой 1000 зерен и их биохимическим составом (белок и клейковина). На основании полученных результатов линии Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Ouasloukos 1, Bicredera1//Oss11/Stj5/3/Ammar и Krupinka были отобраны в качестве перспективных исходных источников для программ селекции твердой пшеницы.

Key words. Durum wheat, breeding, grain quality, thousand kernel weight for thousand kernel weight (TKW), hectoliter weight (HLW), vitreousness (KV), grain protein content (GPC), gluten content (GC), and the gluten deformation index (GDI), correlation.

Kalit so‘zlar. Qattiq bug‘doy, seleksiya, don sifati, 1000 don vazni, natura og‘irligi, shishasimonlik, dondagi oqsil miqdori, kleykovina miqdori, kleykovina deformatsiyasi indeksi (IDK), korrelyatsiya.

Ключевые слова. Твердая пшеница, селекция, качество зерна, масса 1000 зерен, натурная масса, стекловидность, содержание белка в зерне, содержание клейковины, индекс деформации клейковины (ИДК), корреляция.

Introduction. Durum wheat is one of the most important cereal crops, cultivated worldwide on more than 17 million hectares, with an annual production of approximately 38.1 million tons. Canada, Italy, Turkey, the United States, Kazakhstan, Syria, Algeria, France, Morocco, Greece, Spain, and Tunisia are recognized as the leading countries in global durum wheat production [1]. For the food industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the annual demand for durum wheat grain exceeds 400 thousand tons. [2]. Durum wheat grain possesses a range of

technological properties, making it suitable for the production of high-quality semolina, pasta, and various confectionery products. The high protein content and superior gluten quality of durum wheat ensure that products derived from its flour are both nutritionally valuable and of excellent technological quality [3]. At present, durum wheat breeding is focused on the identification and utilization of primary sources possessing superior grain quality, valuable agronomic traits, and resistance to adverse environmental factors, with the aim of developing new cultivars. In this regard, scientific research directed toward the creation of novel durum wheat varieties that combine high grain yield with enhanced technological quality traits is considered of critical importance for breeding programs.

Materials and methods. Field experiments were conducted in 2021 at the irrigated experimental plots of the Central Experimental Farm of the “Scientific Research Institute of Rainfed Agriculture” located in Jizzakh region. Twenty-six durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) lines, selected from the 42nd IDON collection nursery introduced from ICARDA, were sown in October under a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications, using plots of 10 m² each. The cultivar “Makuz-3” was employed as the standard check.

Grain technological quality traits were assessed using the following standards and instruments: Thousand kernel weight (TKW) — GOST 12042-80 (2011), Hectoliter weight (HLW) — via PH-1 method, GOST 10840 (2017), Kernel vitreousness (KV) — GOST 10987-76 (2009), Grain protein content (GPC) — measured using the Perten instrument, Gluten content (GC) and Gluten deformation index (GDI) — GOST 13586.1-86 (2009).

Additional assessments followed the methodologies of VIR (1984) manual. For TKW measurement, two subsamples of 500 seeds each were taken from each durum wheat genotypes and weighed separately with an accuracy of 0.01 g. The difference between replicates did not exceed 5% relative to the average weight, ensuring precision. The HLW was determined using a PH-1 model one-liter volume tester. Prior to measurement, grain samples were sieved with a 6 mm screen and thoroughly homogenized. Two replicates were tested, and the weight difference between them did not exceed 5 g. The trait kernel vitreousness was assessed under laboratory conditions using the DSZ-3 diaphanoscope. For each test, 100 kernels were placed into the cassette and examined under a light source through a lens. The number of fully translucent, partially translucent, and mealy (non-translucent) kernels was recorded. Final vitreousness was calculated by summing the number of fully translucent kernels and half the count of partially translucent ones.

Statistical analyses were conducted using OriginPro 2025b (v10.2.5.212) to evaluate the results obtained from the study and to determine the intercorrelations

among the grain quality parameters of various durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) cultivars and advanced lines.

Results and discussion. In cereal crops, particularly wheat, TKW is an important yield-determining trait, contributing to increased productivity under irrigated conditions [4]. This indicator not only allows the identification of the cultivar to which a wheat sample belongs, but also provides insights into the environmental conditions prevailing during the grain-filling stage of plant development. A higher TKW primarily reflects larger grain size and serves as a trait positively influencing equivalent yield. When the technological quality traits of grains from the control nursery were examined, the following results were obtained: the TKW of the tested lines ranged from 39.8 g to 49.2 g. Based on this parameter, 13 cultivars and lines (Joric 69, Stj 3, Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Sebatel 2, Sbh/4, Bicederaa1//Ossl1/Stj5/3/Ammar8, Ouasloukos 1, Bicederaa 1, and Krupinka) were found to exceed the standard cultivar “Makuz-3” (44.3 g) by 1.1–4.9 g. (Table 1).

HLW represents the weight of grain expressed in grams per liter. The higher the HLW, the greater the amount of useful nutrients contained in the grain, indicating that the kernels are well-developed and fully matured. Grains with higher HLW possess a larger proportion of endosperm and a smaller proportion of bran compared to other grains. Consequently, such grains yield more flour upon milling. Therefore, HLW is considered one of the key indicators of grain quality [5]. The HLW of the cultivar and line samples was observed to range from 773.8 g/L to 815.6 g/L. For the standard cultivar “Makuz-3,” this value was 800.9 g/L. Compared to the standard, 13 cultivars and lines (Joric 69, Stj 3, Ouasloukos 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Icasyr 1/3, Ouasloukos, Ouasloukos 1/5, Icamor TA 0462, Sebatel 2, Ouasloukos 1, and Bicederaa 1) exhibited HLW values higher by 1.3–14.7 g/L (Table 1).

KV is a hereditary trait; however, it is influenced by air temperature and the amount of precipitation. These environmental factors directly affect changes in grain protein content [6]. KV is of significant importance, as it is directly associated with the technological properties of the grain [7]. Durum wheat kernels may be classified as transparent (fully vitreous endosperm), mealy (fully non-vitreous endosperm), or partially vitreous (partially mealy or partially transparent endosperm). In the control nursery, the KV of durum wheat cultivars and lines was observed to range from 71.6% to 88.6%. When the cultivars and lines were grouped according to KV, 15 were classified as low (below 80%), 12 as medium (81–95%), and none as high (above 95%). For the standard cultivar “Makuz-3,” KV was recorded at 79.8%. Compared to the standard, 12 cultivars and lines (Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Sebatel 2, Sbh/4, Bicederaa1//Ossl1/Stj5/3/Ammar8, Ouasloukos 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4),

Bicrederaa 1, Joric 69, Stj 3, Icamor TA 0462, and Krupinka) exhibited higher KV values by 2.0–8.8%. (Table 1).

Protein is one of the key components of wheat grain, determining the nutritional value and dietary quality of its flour. Grain protein content (GPC) is considered the most important indicator, as it influences gluten content (GC), its quality, and also the degree of grain vitreousness. According to Sh. Dilmurodov, the protein and gluten content of durum wheat grain are closely associated with growing conditions, applied agronomic practices, varietal characteristics, and several other factors. [8]. Adverse climatic conditions negatively affect the total protein content and gluten content (GC) of wheat grain, since these two parameters are interrelated [9]. The grain protein content (GPC) of the studied cultivars and lines was found to range between 13.9% and 17.2%. Based on this indicator, the samples were classified into three groups: low (below 12%), medium (12–15%), and high (above 15%). No samples were identified in the low group, while 6 belonged to the medium group and 21 to the high group. For the standard cultivar “Makuz-3,” GPC was recorded at 15.5%. Compared to the standard, nine cultivars and lines (Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Sebatel 2, Sbh/4, Bicrederaa1//Ossl1/Stj5/3/Ammar8, Ouasloukos 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Bicrederaa 1, and Krupinka) exhibited higher GPC values by 0.5–1.7%. (Table 1).

Table 1

Kernels quality traits in durum wheat cultivars and advanced lines

Cultivars and advanced lines	TKW (g)	HLW (g/L)	KV (%)	GPC (%)	GC (%)	GDI (IDK)
Makuz-3(check)	44,30	800,83	79,77	15,47	29,37	85,30
Joric 69	45,40	815,60	81,77	15,83	30,10	100,07
Mrb 3	43,80	795,47	78,90	15,27	29,07	79,97
Ouasloukos 1/5	43,20	808,13	77,80	15,10	28,63	92,60
Mrb 3/Mna 1	39,80	791,37	71,63	13,90	26,37	109,53
Ouasloukos 1	45,42	808,88	81,77	15,60	29,57	95,33
Sebatel 2	48,03	806,07	86,47	16,80	31,83	89,97
Ouasloukos	44,60	809,80	80,33	15,57	29,57	93,73
Stj 3	45,40	813,70	81,77	15,83	30,13	97,63
Mrb 3*	44,40	800,23	79,97	15,50	29,43	84,17
Ter 1//Mrf	49,23	792,30	88,63	17,20	32,63	76,27
Tdicocum 1	48,23	783,43	86,83	16,80	31,97	67,40
Mrb 3/Tdicoccoi	40,80	773,80	73,43	14,23	27,07	57,77
Icamor TA 0462	45,40	807,70	81,77	15,83	30,13	91,60
Icamor TA 0471	43,80	799,33	78,90	15,30	29,03	83,30
Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr	48,03	811,70	79,60	15,40	29,33	95,63
Icasyr 1/3	44,40	810,30	79,97	15,50	29,43	94,23
Maamouri 3	41,63	798,43	74,90	14,50	27,60	82,40
Bicrederaa 1	45,80	802,13	82,50	16,00	30,37	86,07
Sbh/4	46,43	797,73	83,60	16,20	30,77	81,67

Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/	46,23	793,27	83,20	16,10	30,63	76,47
Ouasloukos 1	46,23	804,23	83,20	16,13	30,63	88,17
Baniswaf6/Miki	41,83	794,40	75,27	14,60	27,73	78,37
Bicredera1//Os	46,43	791,17	83,60	16,20	30,77	75,17
Candocross H25	43,20	795,43	77,80	15,10	28,63	78,57
Korifla(DS15/G	44,60	800,33	80,33	15,60	29,57	84,27
Krupinka	49,23	800,23	88,63	17,20	32,63	74,17
Mean Square (Model)	17,84738	286,83372	54,41929	1,98861	7,12342	352,33
Mean Square (Error)	0,71191	19,37882	2,27842	0,11395	0,41235	49,78778
Prob>F	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Coeff Var	0,01875	0,0055	0,01869	0,02156	0,02159	0,08284

TKW = Thousand kernel weight (g), HLW =Hectoliter weight (g/L), KV = Kernel vitreousness (%), GPC = Grain protein content (%), CC = Gluten content (%), GDI = Gluten Deformation Index (IDK)

The water-insoluble protein fraction of wheat flour, upon dough resting, absorbs water and forms a sticky and elastic mass, which constitutes gluten. Gluten content (GC) is a primary indicator of grain quality. The gluten of wheat grain contains proteins such as fibrin, casein, and gliadin. Gluten is defined as the hydrated gel remaining after washing wheat flour dough. Its composition consists mainly of proteins, with small amounts of starch, lipids, fibers, and minerals [10]. The GC of the studied samples was observed to range from 26.4% to 32.6%. When analyzed across five groups, four cultivars and lines were classified as low (20.1–28.0%), and twenty-three as medium (28.1–36.0%), while no samples were identified in the very low (16.0–20.0%), high (36.1–44.0%), or very high (above 44.0%) groups. For the standard cultivar “Makuz-3,” GC was recorded at 29.4%. Compared to the standard, nine samples (Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Sebatel 2, Sbh/4, Bicredera1//Oss11/Stj5/3/Ammar8, Ouasloukos 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Bicredera 1, and Krupinka) exhibited higher GC values by 1.0–3.2% (Table 1).

Under laboratory conditions, gluten quality was determined using the GDI IDK-3 instrument. The GDI index was classified into three categories: Class I – good (45–75), Class II – satisfactory (20–40/80–100), and Class III – unsatisfactory (0–15/105–120 and above). The GDI values of the studied cultivars and lines ranged from 57.8 to 109.5. When analyzed according to these categories, 8 cultivars and lines belonged to Class I (good), 18 to Class II (satisfactory), and 1 to Class III (unsatisfactory). For the standard cultivar “Makuz-3,” the GDI value was recorded at 85.3. Based on the GDI index, 8 lines classified as Class I were selected (Table 1).

Correlation is the statistical relationship between two or more quantitative traits or values. Depending on the direction of influence between traits, the correlation may be positive or negative. If the change in one trait does not affect the change in another, such a relationship is not considered a correlation [11].

Figure 1. Intercorrelative relationship of technological quality traits in durum wheat grain.

Based on the obtained results, the degree of association among the studied traits was analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The correlation matrix indicated that while some quality traits exhibited strong positive relationships, others showed weak or nearly negligible associations. A perfect positive correlation ($r = 1$) was observed between grain protein content (GPC) and gluten content (GC). This expected result confirms that an increase in grain protein content directly leads to a proportional increase in gluten content. A very strong correlation ($r = 0.96$) was found between thousand kernel weight (TKW) and kernel vitreousness (KV), reflecting that larger grains are naturally heavier and better filled. Furthermore, TKW showed a strong positive correlation with both protein content ($r = 0.91$) and gluten content ($r = 0.91$). A similar trend was observed for kernel vitreousness (KV) ($r = 0.95$). This indicates that in the studied samples, the larger and more fully developed the grain, the greater the accumulation of nutritional substances (protein and gluten). This is an important trait for breeding, since yield and quality are usually negatively correlated, whereas in this case a synergistic relationship was observed. An average positive correlation ($r = 0.64$) was found between hectoliter weight (HLW) and gluten deformation index (GDI). This suggests that the higher the grain density (test weight), the more likely the gluten quality (deformation index) is to change accordingly, although the relationship is not strictly linear. HLW showed very weak correlations with other major quality traits such as TKW, KV, GPC, and GC ($r =$

0.13–0.19). This indicates that test weight is not directly related to protein content or thousand kernel weight, but rather develops as an independent trait. No significant correlation was observed between TKW and GDI ($r = 0.01$). Very weak negative correlations were found between GDI and KV, GPC, and GC ($r = -0.04$ to -0.09). This suggests that increases in grain protein and gluten content do not substantially affect gluten quality (its elasticity), or may show a slight tendency to decrease, though the effect is statistically negligible (Figure 1).

Conclusions and recommendations. Based on the technological quality traits of durum wheat, the varieties and lines Ter 1//Mrf, Tdicocum 1, Miki 3 (Stj//Bcr/Lks4), Ouasloukos 1, Bicredera1//Ossl1/Stj5/3/Ammar, and Krupinka were highly evaluated for grain quality and selected.

Correlation analysis revealed a strong synergy between grain size (TKW) and its biochemical composition (GPC, GC) in the studied wheat varieties. This provides scientific evidence that it is possible to simultaneously develop large grains with high protein content during the breeding process. At the same time, gluten quality (GDI) was found to be an independent trait, varying regardless of grain size and protein content.

The durum wheat lines selected above are proposed as valuable initial sources for breeding programs aimed at creating new genotypes with enhanced grain quality.

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